

SONG INSPIRED INSTRUCTION: IT'S CONTRIBUTION IN ENHANCING VOCABULARY DEVELOPMENT

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Song Inspired Instruction: It's Contribution in Enhancing Vocabulary Development

Ivy Flor Lauron Tapic*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The main concern of this study was to use an alternate way of teaching students how to understand meaning of words from a selection read. It aimed to determine the learning contribution of Song-Inspired Instructions in enhancing vocabulary development of the Grade 6 pupils at Corpus Christi Parochial School of Iligan, Tubod, Iligan City. This study employed the quasi-experimental research design. The data on performances of pupils were gathered using a 40-item researcher-made tests. The participants of the study were 60 Grade VI pupils, 30 placed on the control group and 30 on the experimental group. Based on the data gathered, the results showed that the pretest of both groups with 0.024 p.value exceeded at 0.05 level of significance was not rejected and it revealed that there were no significant differences in the mean pretest scores of the participants. It was concluded that the use of the Song-Inspired Instructions had improved the pupils' vocabulary knowledge. This proved that using Song-Inspired Instructions can be adapted as other teaching strategy in vocabulary enhancement. Thus, it is hoped that the training-workshop program on Song-Inspired Instructions be realized.

Keywords: *song inspired instruction, enhancing vocabulary development*

Introduction

Every child has a different learning style. Through constant practice, a child becomes proficient in a learning area. Some children learn by imitating, some learn by doing, others learn by studying, while others still, learn by using alternative styles, e.g. dancing, acting, and singing. However, with the advancement of technology, books and other reading materials are already neglected. Children spend a lot of time playing video games and worst, does not come to school anymore. And so now, teachers are challenged to use different techniques and strategies to be able to cope with the demands of motivating students to go back to reading.

English is one of the most powerful languages used in our society today. It is used in schools, businesses, Internet, job applications and in the field of research. In school, English as a subject includes listening, speaking, writing, and reading. These four skills need a strong vocabulary competence for each to be mastered. When a student reads a lot, he/she is able to learn new words. These new words then can be used when the student writes a sentence or a paragraph.

For a child to communicate well, both in written and oral form, the child must have a very good vocabulary knowledge. When a child fully grasped the meaning of the words used in a reading material or lyrics of a song, the child write comprehensive sentences using these words. In this regard, song-inspired instructions will be conducted to help learners use an alternate way of fully understanding the meaning of a text being read or sung.

As mentioned by Maslina (2015) vocabulary is very important for other skills such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing because without vocabulary we cannot understand what someone said. If we do not comprehend what someone has said, we are unable to communicate our ideas or repeat them. Without vocabulary, we are unable to comprehend the text and produce any written work, which is essential for reading and writing skills.

He further said that improving vocabulary is one of difficult competence, but it is very important. If learners do not know how to expand their vocabulary, they gradually lose interest in learning. They typically lack enthusiasm for learning the English language since they regard it as a boring and challenging subject. As a result, the majority of students find it difficult to learn English, and despite attending English classes, they are not motivated to do so. Therefore, in English language lessons, songs can be utilized directly to teach vocabulary.

Realizing how crucial vocabulary development is for students, it is of great importance to develop this ability. To achieve it, new words should be introduced by implementing the best method and techniques provided by theories. Thus, this study aimed on using songs as a tool to help learners improve their vocabulary. This will focus on the Grade 6 pupils of Corpus Christi Parochial School of Iligan, Inc.

As an English teacher, the researcher has seen the difficulties the students have in recognizing meaning of words which hinders them from using words correctly in both written and oral activities. This study then will be conducted to give pupils a new and alternate way of learning, understanding, and using words correctly.

Research Questions

The main thrust of this study was to determine the effectiveness of videoke in improving children's reading proficiency. It also aimed to let students use different techniques in improving their reading skills. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following question:

1. What are the pretest scores in the traditional and song-inspired groups?
2. What are the posttest in the traditional and song-inspired groups?
3. What are the pretest and posttest scores in both the traditional and song-inspired groups?
4. Is there a significant difference of the pretest scores in the traditional and song-inspired groups?
5. Is there significant difference of the posttest scores in the traditional and song-inspired groups?
6. Is there a significant difference between the pre and post performances of both the traditional and song-inspired groups?
7. What training program for teacher can be devised from the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The method used in this study was the quasi-experimental research design using two groups of subjects, the traditional and song-inspired groups. The teacher-made test was the main tool in gathering the data needed. Both groups of pupils were composed of heterogeneous grouping of below average, average, and above average achievement levels.

Participants

The participants of the study were the Grade VI pupils of Corpus Christi Parochial School of Iligan. There were 30 pupils in each group from 2 sections. Both sections have heterogeneous grouping.

Once the subjects were chosen, tossing of coin was done to determine who among them will belong to the Traditional group and Videoke group. The head side was the Control group, and the tail side was the Treatment group.

Instruments

This study utilized a research-made test which aimed to test skills in vocabulary knowledge of students. There were 40 multiple choice test items in conducting the pretest and posttest. The researcher made test was item analyzed in order to determine the reliability coefficient, the index of difficulty and index of discrimination for the validation of each item. The same items were given on the posttest, but the questions were reshuffled.

The pilot test was conducted at Queen of Angels School of Iligan to validate the questionnaires. The subjects were the grade 6 pupils who were officially enrolled and were not the subjects of the study.

Procedure

The researcher gave a letter of request to the school principal to be permitted to conduct her study in their school. All the communication were duly signed and approved by the concerned personalities. After getting the approval, the researcher made a committee of English Grade VI teachers to choose and prepare the songs used by the subjects.

The researcher grouped the Grade VI pupils into two groups. One group was named the Traditional Group while the other group was named the Song-Inspired Group. Each group went through the same lesson for a month, but one group used the song-inspired instruction while the other group used the traditional method to complete the whole duration of the study.

Development of Lesson Plan

There were two sets of lesson plan used in this study. The skills and objectives were the same. They only differ on the way they were presented, and the activities used.

Preparation of TOS

Before making the test item, the researcher prepared a table of Specification to know the proper placement of the test items in the questionnaire and to determine the content sampling and item validity of the test. The Table of Specification will follow Bloom's Taxonomy Model which includes 60% easy, 30% average and 10% difficult items.

Development of Pretest and Posttest

The researcher prepared a 50-item multiple-choice researcher made test used in conducting the pretest and posttest. The test questionnaire was treated and validated for reliability.

Before these questions were finalized, the researcher asked valuable insights and perusal from other English teachers. Validation and testing for its reliability were done by pilot testing of Grade 6 students at Queen of Angels School of Iligan, Inc.

Item Analysis

The researcher prepared a 50-item multiple choice test which was analyzed to determine the index of difficulty and index of discrimination. It was piloted to the Grade 6 pupils of Queen of Angels School of Iligan, Inc. Each result was item analyzed to determine which of them was retained, revised, or rejected.

Among the 50 questions, 10 were rejected. These were items 2, 12, 16, 21, 23, 24, 29, 34, 42 and 44. There were 9 items that were revised which were items 4, 10, 11, 15, 18, 28, 30, 33 and 45. The rest of the items were retained. The total number of items used in the final study was 40.

Administration of Pretest

After the approval of the thesis adviser, the researcher administered the Pretest to both groups. The subjects were given the pretest prior to conducting the study and before teaching the prepared topic. During the pretest day, the researcher explained how the test will be answered and assured the students that their answers will be confidential. All the results were recorded, tabulated, and kept for further use.

Conduct of the Experiment of the Two Approaches

In the traditional teaching, lecture method by discussion in front of class using chalk and chalk board were used. This was done during their English time class inside their classroom.

In the song-inspired instruction approach, the lessons where the vocabulary words were taken were from songs which the pupils sung. The computer room was utilized for each session. This was done during their intervention time from 3:00 to 4:00 in the afternoon of the same day.

Administering the Posttest

After one month of completing the lesson, a posttest will be given to group of subjects. The contents of the test were the same but were reshuffled. The results were interpreted to determine the effectiveness song-inspired instruction in improving vocabulary knowledge.

Analysis of Pretest and Posttest

The results of the pretest and posttest were recorded and tallied for the interpretation on the research study.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used to analyze the data:

The first tool was Frequency and Percentage Tool. It was used to describe the distribution of the pretest and posttest scores of the subjects in the traditional and song-inspired groups for Problems 1,2 and 3.

The second tool used was Independent T-test. This was used to determine the differences on the pretest and posttest scores of the subjects between the traditional and song-inspired groups in Problems 4 and 5.

The last tool was Paired T-test. This was used to determine the differences between the pretest and posttest of the subjects in the traditional and song-inspired groups in Problem 6.

Results and Discussion

This section includes the presentation, analysis and interpretation of results and discussions from the data gathered by the researcher.

PROBLEM 1: What are the pretest scores in the Traditional and Song- Inspired Groups?

Table 1. *Pretest Scores in the Traditional and Song-Inspired Group*

MPS	Performance Category	Traditional Group		Song-Inspired Group	
		F	%	F	%
75%-100%	Mastered	11	37%	10	33%
50%-74%	Nearing Mastery	14	47%	14	47%
49%-below	Least Mastered	5	17%	6	20%
TOTAL		30	100%	30	100%
<i>Mean</i>		<i>26.167</i>		<i>26.200</i>	

Table 1 (Figure 1) presents the pretest scores of students in the Traditional and Song-inspired groups. The data implies that the subjects in the two groups have an equal conceptual standing at the start of the experiment. Both groups have students that belong to the least mastered category, 17% on the control group and 20% on the experimental group. It also shows that both groups have the same number of students in the nearing mastery category at 47%.

With these result, Mohamad and Amin (2011) said that one of the main assumptions in the validity of the test involved in research was the same ability of the learners both in the control and experimental group.

Figure 1. Pretest Scores in the Traditional and Song-Inspired Group

PROBLEM 2: What are the posttest scores in the Traditional and Song-Inspired Group?

Table 2 (Figure 2) shows the difference in the results of the students’ posttest scores in the Traditional and Song-inspired groups. The data shows that 97% of the traditional group subjects have reached the mastered level while 93% of the song-inspired group have reached that level. Although the percentage is higher on the traditional group, the mean score is higher on the song-inspired group since the scores of the pupils on the experimental group have improved well from their pretest to posttest results compared to the control group.

Table 2. Posttest Scores in the Traditional and Song-Inspired Group

MPS	Performance Category	Traditional Group		Song-Inspired Group	
		F	%	F	%
75%-100%	Mastered	29	97%	28	93%
50%-74%	Nearing Mastery	1	3%	2	7%
49%-below	Least Mastered	0	0%	0	0%
TOTAL		30	100%	30	100%
<i>Mean</i>		34.43		36.70	

Figure 2. Posttest Scores in the Traditional and Song-Inspired Group

As Silverman and Hines (2009) in their study said that the use of multimedia to enhance read alouds and vocabulary instruction for English language learners (ELL) and English-speaking students was narrowed not only for the targeted vocabulary words but for general vocabulary knowledge as well. This means that when students are given intervention, they are able to enhance their learned vocabulary words not only in defining them but by using them in both written and oral language.

PROBLEM 3: What are the pretest and the posttest scores in the Traditional and Song-Inspired Group?

Table 3 (Figure 3) presents the pretest and the posttest scores in the Traditional and Song-Inspired Groups. The data show a significant increase in the results of the posttest in both the control and experimental groups. This implies that there is learning in each group using two different methods. As Liu and Long (2007) said that traditional approach can also increase the performance of the learners because teacher’s action and language become the target initiated.

However, the achievement of the experiment group, measured by the difference between the pretest and the posttest, mean is better than that of the control group. In a similar investigative study by Kim et al. (2008), the results showed that participants learned better when they received visual text and added graphics or visual text, added spoken text, and added graphics instruction. The results lead one to conclude that an effective way to improve learning of English vocabulary is to offer graphics that illustrate what the vocabulary

means.

Table 3. *Pretest and the posttest scores in the Traditional and Song-Inspired Group*

MPS	Performance Category	Traditional Group		Song-Inspired Group					
		pretest F	%	posttest F	%	pretest F	%	posttest F	%
75%-100%	Mastered	11	37%	29	97%	10	33%	28	93%
50%-74%	Nearing Mastery	14	47%	1	3%	14	47%	2	7%
49%-below	Least Mastered	5	17%	0	0%	6	20%	0	0%
TOTAL		30	100%	30	100%	30	100%	30	100%
<i>Mean</i>		26.167 34.43		26.200 36.70					

Figure 3. *Pretest and the posttest scores in the Traditional and Song-Inspired Group*

PROBLEM 4: Is there a significant difference of the pretest scores in the Traditional and Song-inspired groups?

Table 4 (Figure 4) presents the comparison of paired differences on the pretest scores of the Traditional and Song-Inspired Groups. This show the p-value of .983 exceeded at the 0.05 level of significance (2-tailed) which means that Ho1 is accepted, and it reveals that there are no significant differences in the mean pretest scores between the control and experimental groups.

This implies that at the beginning of the experiment, the two groups have comparable mean score differences in their pretest performance. Furthermore, it is an indication of good comparison since the two groups show insignificant performances prior to the treatment.

As supported by Cooper (2014) pupils have working memory which is like the brain’s notepad where new information is held temporarily and when the details are useful, then it will become long-term memory that can be strengthened and recalled.

Table 4. *Differences between the pretest scores in the Traditional and Song-Inspired Group*

Group	Pretest Scores		Mean Difference	t-value	p-value	Remark
	Mean	SD				
Traditional Group	26.167	5.82	.033	.021	.983	Not Significant
Song-Inspired Group	26.200	6.43				

Note1: n=30: Analysis is based on independent T-test SD - standard deviation

Figure 4. Cylindrical Plot on the Pupil's pretest scores in the Traditional and Song-Inspired Groups

PROBLEM 5: Is there significant difference of the posttest scores in the Traditional and Song-inspired groups?

Table 5 (Figure 5) presents the comparison paired differences on the posttest scores of the Traditional and Song-Inspired Groups. This shows a p-value of 0.024 which is lesser than that 0.05 level of significance. This means that Ho2 is rejected and reveals that there are significant differences in the mean posttest scores of the pupils between the Traditional and Song-Inspired Groups.

Table 5. Differences between the posttest scores in the Traditional and Song-Inspired Group

Group	Posttest Scores		Mean Difference	t-value	p-value	Remark
	Mean	SD				
Traditional Group	34.43	3.73	2.27	2.310	.024	Significant
Song-Inspired Group	36.70	3.87				

Note1: n=30: Analysis is based on independent T-test

SD - standard deviation

Figure 5. Cylindrical Plot on the Pupil's Posttest scores in the Traditional and Song-Inspired Groups

Additionally, this implies that the song-inspired group performed better compared to the traditional group. Therefore, pupils in the Song-inspired Instruction performed better than the pupils in the traditional method. This supports to the finding of Espinosa (2014) who stated that it gives students' the opportunity to explore their understanding and make new sense of new ideas. Similarly, Kim et al. (2008) concluded from their study that an effective way to improve learning English vocabulary is to offer graphics that illustrate what the vocabulary means.

PROBLEM 6: Is there a significant difference between the pre and post performances of both the Traditional and Song-inspired groups?

Table 6 (Figure 6) represents the comparison of paired differences on the pretest and posttest scores of the subjects in both the Traditional and Song-Inspired Group. As shown in the table, the level of significance (2 tailed) using paired sample test in both groups is 0.000 which is lesser than the accepted value of of 0.05, thus, Ho3 is rejected for both results.

This implies that in the Traditional group pupil’s vocabulary knowledge has increased as quoted by the statement of Sevilla, Segra, Podhorski, Guruceaga, Mato, Martinez-Cruz & Rubio (2005) that any method can be effective as long as the teachers are comfortable with it and is suited to the type of learners that you are dealing with.

Table 6. Differences between the pretest and posttest scores in the Traditional and Song-Inspired Group

Paired	Mean	SD	Paired Mean Difference	t-value	p-value	Remark
Traditional Group						
Pretest	26.1667	5.82				
Posttest	34.400	3.72	-8.233	-8.955	.000	Significant
Song-Inspired Group						
Pretest	26.20	6.43				
Posttest	30.70	3.87	-10.50	-9.357	.000	Significant

Figure 6. Cylindrical Plot on the Pupil’s Pretest and Posttest scores in the Traditional and Song-Inspired Groups

Likewise in the Song-Inspired Group pupils vocabulary knowledge has increased significantly as suggested by Edwards (2012) that when emergent readers see printed words in the text again and again, they come to identify those words and phrases by their similarities and configurations.

PROBLEM 7: What training program for teacher can be devised from the results of the study?

Based on the result of the study, the researcher suggests conducting a Song-Inspired Instruction Training Workshop for teachers to use in teaching vocabulary. This method will help lessen the pupils in the least mastered category and eventually have all students under the mastered category in terms of vocabulary knowledge. The persons involved for this training workshop will be the English teachers who belong to the Diocese of Iligan and the teachers from Queen of Angel School of Iligan, Inc. This will be evaluated by the school principal of each participating school and the Diocesan Superintendent.

Table 7. Proposed Training Program

Program Title : 3-Day Training Workshop on Song-Inspired Instruction to improve vocabulary			
Rationale: This training will be conducted to introduce to teachers the Song-Inspired Instruction in teaching vocabulary. This will also give teachers an alternate way of teaching students how to learn, understand and use words correctly both in oral and written language.			
Resource Speakers : Ivy Flor L. Tapic Clariza M. Jandayan			
Objectives: At the end of the training workshop, the teachers are expected to:			
1. Use the Song-Inspired Instruction in teaching vocabulary.			
2. Gain mastery of Making Song Inspired Instruction materials as a method in teaching vocabulary.			
3. Develop their own PowerPoint for songs that will be used in their class.			
Activities / Topics	Time Allotment	Venue	Person’s Involved
DAY 1			
Arrival and Registration	7:30 -8:00	Corpus Christi Basement	Attendance Committee QASI Faculty
Preliminary Activities Presentation of Participants	8:00 – 9:00	Corpus Christi	Teacher Jennylou

Introduction of Song-Inspired Instruction and 21st Century Skills	9:00 – 10:00	Basement Corpus Christi Basement	Sharmaine E. Butalid Ivy Flor L. Tapic
Health Break	10:00 – 10:30		
Lecture: Vocabulary Knowledge and its impact to oral and written language.	10:30 – 12:00	Corpus Christi Basement	Ivy Flor L. Tapic
LUNCH BREAK			
Afternoon Praise	1:00 – 1:30	Corpus Christi Basement	CCPSI Faculty
Lecture: Guidelines in Choosing Songs for the Song-Inspired Instruction	1:30 – 2:30	Corpus Christi Basement	Participants / Teachers
Workshop: Choosing songs which relates to the target objective of the lesson	2:30 – 3:30	Corpus Christi Basement	Ivy Flor L. Tapic
Health Break	3:30 – 3:45		
Reporting : Songs to be used in the Song-Inspired Instruction	3:45 – 5:00	Corpus Christi Basement	Participants / Teachers
DAY 2			
Activities / Topics	Time Allotment	Venue	Person's Involved
Morning Praise / Recapitulation	7:30 -8:30	Corpus Christi Basement	QASI Faculty
Lecture: Guidelines in Formulating Song-Inspired Instruction	8:30 – 9:30	Corpus Christi Basement	Ivy Flor L. Tapic
Health Break	9:30 – 10:00		
Workshop: Formulating Song-Inspired Instruction	10:00 – 11:00	Corpus Christi Basement	Ivy Flor L. Tapic
Reporting of the Output	11:00 – 12:00	Corpus Christi Basement	Participants
LUNCH BREAK			
Afternoon Praise	1:00 – 1:30	Corpus Christi Basement	CCPSI Faculty
Workshop: Creating a Lesson Plan based on the outputs that were reported	1:30 – 3:00	Corpus Christi Basement	Participants / Teachers
Health Break	3:00 – 3:30		
Open Forum	3:30 – 4:30	Corpus Christi Basement	Participants / Teachers
Clearing House of Ideas/Closing Prayer	4:30 – 5:00	Corpus Christi Basement	Participants / Teachers
DAY 3			
Morning Praise / Recapitulation	7:30 -8:30	Corpus Christi Basement	QASI Faculty
Lecture: Guidelines in Creating PowerPoint for Songs to be used in class	8:30 – 10:00	Corpus Christi Basement	Teacher Clariza M. Jandayan
Health Break	10:00 – 10:30		
Workshop: Creating PowerPoint for Songs to be used in class	10:30 – 12:00	Corpus Christi Basement	Participants / Teachers
LUNCH BREAK			
Demo Teaching on using Song-Inspired Instruction in teaching vocabulary	1:00 – 2:30	Corpus Christi Basement	Participants / Teachers
Exhibit of Output by School	2:30 – 3:00	Corpus Christi Basement	Participants / Teachers
Health Break	3:00 – 3:30		
Giving of Feedback on the Training-workshop	3:30 - 4:00	Corpus Christi Basement	Participants / Teachers
Closing Program/Giving	4:00 – 5:00	Corpus Christi Basement	Participants / Teachers

Conclusions

Based on the findings drawn from the study, it concludes that there were no significant difference on the mean pretest scores of the subjects between the Traditional and Song-Inspired Groups. These show that both groups have quite similar performances before the treatment.

However, there was a significant difference in the mean scores in the posttest in both the traditional and Song-Inspired method. Between the traditional and Song-Inspired group, the latter performed better in the posttest as mentioned by Lynch (2005) that a variety of new vocabulary can be introduced to students through songs. Songs, according to him, are almost always directed to the native-speaking population so they usually contain contemporary vocabulary, idioms and expressions as it boosts student vocabulary with useful phrases, vocabulary and expressions.

The Theory of Multiple Intelligences by Gardner (1983) has relevance to the present study because students are not only limited to one teaching strategy. They are able to learn using different teaching techniques like using song-inspired instructions in improving vocabulary.

The Whole Language/Natural Learning Theory by Goodman (1986) has relevance to the present study because as a teacher it is vital that you use a range of strategies when teaching spelling and vocabulary. This theory highlights the importance of varying your teaching approaches depending on the context of the words you are getting your students to learn and embracing cross-curricular activities that promote holistic learning. It also suggests that teachers should make learning relevant to students' lives and the skills they will need to possess in order to function effectively within the community.

The Behavioural Theory by Skinner (1974) has relevance to the present study because it is basically a teacher's responsibility to create classroom activities like using songs in teaching vocabulary which embraces spelling and vocabulary development.

Seeing the result of the study, it can be concluded that the Song-Inspired Instruction approach is more effective than the traditional approach. In the traditional Approach, students learn vocabulary using the traditional way of teaching- reading books on your own. Traditional Method also utilizes the use of synonym, antonyms and context clues which are also effective way of learning the meaning of words.

However, with the advancement of technology, the use of multimedia instructions like the song-inspired instruction is not only appealing to the 21st century learners but are also more effective as picture clues are used. Aside from letting students sing along with their favorite songs, they are able to comprehend what they are singing as pictures on the videos are shown. As supported in the study of Verhallen (2010) both treatments benefited receptive and expressive vocabularies; however, readings with the addition of video were found to be especially effective for expressive L2 vocabulary acquisition.

Based on the findings drawn and conclusions made, the study offer the following recommendations for considerations:

School Administrators may provide support to teachers in terms of sending teachers to seminar and trainings for them to acquire and learn new and innovative ways and techniques in teaching vocabulary.

Curriculum Planners may also help them in making recommendations on the role of teachers, parents, and pupils in relation to strategies and approaches in vocabulary development of students.

Teachers may use songs or other techniques as one of the methods in giving instructions and activities in class.

Students may appreciate and understand the lessons they learn since they understand the words that are included in the lesson and are able to use them in oral and written language. They may also be motivated to learn as they are also able to sing their favorite songs at the same time. This will also allow them to write a song of their own.

Future Researchers may use this and serve as basis and benchmark for further similar studies to be undertaken along the line of intervention for vocabulary development.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Ivy Flor Lauron Tapic

Queen of Angels School of Iligan, Inc. – Philippines